
RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SPIRITUAL INVOLVEMENT, SOCIAL SUPPORT AND PERCEIVED STRESS AMONG THE CHRISTIAN CLERGY IN MAKURDI, BENUE STATE, NIGERIA

BY

Frederick Akor Edache

Postgraduate Student, Department of Psychology,
Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi

Email: mcfredericksakoredache@gmail.com

Phone Number: +234 816 795 0330

ABSTRACT

This study investigated the relationship between spiritual involvement and social support on perceived stress among the Christian clergy in Makurdi, Benue State. The study adopted a correlational survey design. One hundred and sixty (160) participants were sampled using stratified sampling technique. The spiritual Involvement and Beliefs Scale, Perceived Stress Scale and Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support were used for data collection. Three hypotheses were formulated and tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation. The result of hypothesis one indicated a negative significant relationship between spiritual involvement and perceived stress among the Christian clergy in Makurdi, Benue State. Also, the result of hypothesis two indicated a negative significant relationship between social support and perceived stress among the Christian clergy in Makurdi, Benue State. For hypothesis three, it was observed that there was a significant positive relationship between spiritual involvement and social support among the Christian clergy in Makurdi, Benue State. It was concluded that spiritual involvement and social support are resources that help to strengthen the Christian clergy in the storms of stress. The study therefore recommended among others that churches should collaborate with family therapist to offer sessions to all members of the clergy.

Key Words: Spiritual Involvement, Social Support, Perceived Stress, Christian Clergy

Background

In recent years, increasing attention has been given to the psychological and emotional resources that individuals draw upon to cope with perceived life's stressors. Perceived stress is the adverse reaction people experience in response to excessive pressure or other types of demands placed on them. In other words, perceived stress describes situations that people perceive to be overwhelming and difficult to cope with (Campbell, 2016). The experience of perceived stress is therefore founded on an encounter with some event or stimulus which is referred to as perceived stressor (Basavanthappa, 2020). Perceived stressors can either be positive or negative and the interpretation given to the perceived stressor is what makes a situation perceived stressful or not. When people perceive situations to be negative, it becomes perceived stressful to them and vice versa. Perceived stress is universal in the sense that all people are inevitably exposed to different situations on daily basis irrespective of their unique demographic characteristics as all people try to adjust to the ever-changing human society (Bukoye, 2017; Fosu-Ayarkwah & Fia 2018; Ramachandiran & Dhanapal, 2018).

Among the Christian clergy, perceived stress can result from rigid work schedules, bureaucracy, denominational structures, conflicts between personal and congregational needs, high congregational expectations and conflicted personal relationships (Doolittle, 2020). Although religion has been known to be a major source of coping during adverse situations, it is surprising to note that most religious people like the Christian clergy go through diverse form of perceived stressors on a daily basis which affects their overall well-being and quality of life (Nortey, 2019). The import from the views expressed is that the Christian clergy go through varied perceived stressors which have the tendency to affect their lives. Religious work such as pastoral work is riddled with an incredible number of work-related perceived stressors and pressures. Potential for perceived stress is increased when there is little time to recover from the strains of workload and emotional perceived stress. Several authors have therefore claimed that perceived stress is a common condition among the Christian clergy (Burnette, 2016; Wong, 2015). This is because Christian clergy are subject to work-related pressures that are typical of other human service occupations. Research has shown that there is a strong and consistent relationship between perceived stress and job demands (Schaufeli, & Bakker, 2022).

In Africa, the Christian clergy play an enormous role in the society such as providing social services, generating economic development projects, and engaging in community development in Sub-Saharan countries such as Nigeria, Kenya, Ghana, and many others (Heaton, et al., 2019; McCain, 2016). In spite of this, there are several reports of high perceived stress among the Christian clergy which affect the health and overall quality of life of the Christian clergy (Proeschold-Bell et al., 2013; Wallace et al., 2021). In Nigeria, the situation is no different as there have been reports of high perceived stress among the Christian clergy (Anyetey, 2018; Nortey, 2019).

Among the many coping mechanisms explored, spiritual involvement and social support have emerged as significant psychosocial shields against stress. Spiritual involvement, which involves prayer, scripture reading, church participation, and a strong sense of connection with God, is often regarded as both a source of strength and a potential stress buffer for clergy. Studies have shown that high levels of spiritual engagement are associated with lower perceived stress, greater emotional resilience, and improved coping outcomes (Hardy et al., 2019; Yonker et al., 2022). However, recent findings also indicate that when spiritual practices are performed out of obligation rather than conviction, or when

spiritual expectations become overwhelming, they can contribute to spiritual fatigue and higher stress levels (Ziemer et al., 2020).

Relatedly, social support which is defined as the perceived availability of emotional, informational, or practical help from others has been identified as a protective factor against stress (Myers et al., 2020). Thoits (2019) had argued that Social Support has direct reducing influence on perceived stress on the Christian clergy. Social Support has been severally linked to reduced perceived stress among the Christian clergy (Ayukosok, 2019; De Almeida et al., 2018; Greczanik & Lupico, 2016). For Christian clergy, social support may come from family, fellow clergy, congregants, denominational networks, or close friends. Recent findings indicate that higher levels of perceived social support are significantly associated with lower levels of stress and burnout among clergy, as such support helps mitigate feelings of isolation, enhances coping capacity, and fosters emotional resilience (Proeschold-Bell & Byassee, 2018; Visker et al., 2021). However, clergy who lack strong support systems or experience conflict within their congregations are more likely to report higher perceived stress and increased risk of burnout (Frenk, 2019).

However, most of the existing studies were conducted in the Western countries, which calls for validation in the developing countries such as Nigeria. In order to formulate effective coping strategies on perceived stress among the Christian clergy in Nigeria and also to control perceived stress usually experienced by the Christian clergy, there is need for studies on spiritual involvement and social support on perceived stress and its mediating link among Nigerian Christian clergy in Makurdi, Benue State.

Method

Design

The study adopted a correlation survey design to investigate the relationship between Spiritual involvement and social support on perceived stress among the Christian clergy in Makurdi, Benue State. This design was considered because correlation design provides the insight into the relationship of various characteristics, attitudes, behaviors, or opinions within the population at that moment paraphrase.

Population

A population is made up of all conceivable element, subject or observation relating to a particular phenomenon of interest of the research subject or element. In this study, the population comprised the Christian clergy from Christian churches or ministries in Makurdi, Benue State, Nigeria and the total population of Christian clergy in Makurdi, Benue State as of January, 2025 estimated to be two hundred and sixty-seven (267) ordained Christian clergy men and women spread across several council wards as shown below covering the population for the study. This estimated sample was determined from the Catholic diocese of Makurdi with about 70 Diocesan Priests, 120 ministers in the Universal Reformed Christian Church (URCC) with its local acronym as NKST and 77 from the Pentecostal fellowship of Nigeria.

Participants

The participants for this study comprised 160 Christian clergy men and women in Makurdi, Benue State within the age range of 23 to 70 years, mean age of 2.15 and standard deviation of .498 and who are practicing as Christian clergy in Makurdi, Benue State.

Sampling Technique

Purposive sampling technique was used to obtain a representation of a sample from the population. Purposive sampling technique is a non-probability sampling technique where

the researcher intentionally selects participants based on specific characteristics relevant to research questions.

The purposive sampling technique was employed for the sampling and selection of the participants from multiple churches and ministries in Makurdi, Benue State who met the inclusion criteria for the study. Hence, the design was correlation research design. The sample was drawn from the estimated population of Christian clergy in Makurdi, Benue State and they comprised ordained Christian clergy men and women spread across several council wards as shown below covering the study.

S/N	Council Wards	NUMBER
1	Agan	16
2	Bar	16
3	Central or South Mission	16
4	Clerk or Market	16
5	Fiidi	16
6	Mbalagh	16
7	Modern Market	16
8	North Bank 1	16
9	North Bank 11	16
10	Wailomayo	16
TOTAL		160

The inclusion criteria include:

- i. Christian clergy with at least two years of formal or informal pastoral counseling and English-speaking skill. This is to ensure better organization and management of the clergy.
- ii. Christian clergy who was interested and willing to participate in the study.
- iii. Christian clergy male and female between the age range of 23 to 70 years. In Nigeria, the legal ordained age for Christian clergy generally falls within the range of 25 for the priesthood and 23 for the diaconate and a retirement age of 70 for most churches.

Exclusion Criteria:

Christian clergy with less than two years of formal or informal pastoral counseling and who were not proficient in English-speaking skill was excluded from the study. This is to ensure that the clergy recruited for this study have enough experience in pastoral work and also can be able to fill the research instruments. Also, clergy under age 23 and clergy above age 70 were not involved in the study because of inexperience for younger clergy and possible retirement for the older ones.

Instruments

The instruments used in this study are: The Spiritual Involvement and Beliefs Scale developed by Hatch et al. (1998), Perceived stress Scale developed by Cohen et al. (1983), and Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support (MSPSS) developed by Gregory et al. (1988).

- i. **The Spiritual Involvement and Beliefs Scale (SIBS):** The Spiritual Involvement and Beliefs Scale (SIBS) was developed by Hatch et al., (1998) to assess spirituality and was designed to be widely applicable across religious traditions, to assess actions as well as beliefs, to address key components not assessed in other available measures,

and to be easily administered and scored. Hatch et al., (1998) reported alpha coefficient of 0.73 to .86 and one-week test retest of 0.78 to 0.90. Chidozie & Chidiebere (2024) reported .77 internal consistency of the scale which made it reliable and valid for use in this study. The researcher conducted a pilot study and obtained .93 internal consistency of the scale which made it reliable and valid for use in the study.

- ii. **Perceived Stress Scale (PSS-10):** The Perceived Stress Scale (PSS-10) is a 10-item questionnaire originally developed by Cohen et al., (1983). It is widely used to assess perceived stress levels in young people and adults aged 12 years and above. It is a self-report questionnaire that was designed to measure the degree to which situations in one's life are appraised as perceived stressful. It evaluates the degree to which an individual has perceived life as unpredictable, uncontrollable and overloading over the previous month. The instrument, however, reported a reliability coefficient (Cronbach alpha) of .62; split half =.63. The researcher conducted a pilot study and obtained .80 internal consistency of the scale which made it reliable and valid for use in the study.
- iii. **Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support (MSPSS):** Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support (MSPSS) was developed by developed by Gregory et al. (1988). The Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support (MSPSS) is a 12 item self-report survey that measures how much social support a person perceives they receive from family, friends, and significant others. Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support (MSPSS) was validated in Nigeria by Bello et al., (2022) and reported Cronbach's coefficient of ($\alpha = .93$), with a Spearman-Brown coefficient of .86 and Guttman Split-Half coefficient of .90. This shows that MSPSS is a reliable measure for social support for the Nigerian population.

Procedure

The researcher obtained a letter of introduction from the Head of Department of Psychology, Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi formerly known as Benue State University and presented it to the various churches and ministries in Makurdi, Benue State with the intention to carry out the research which was used as baseline permission for sampling the participants. The researcher recruited a research assistant who was trained on the purpose and objectives of the study including how to administer and collect data from the participants. One hundred and sixty (160) participants in the age range of 18 to 85 years were recruited. The purpose of the study was explained to the participants and they were assured that information provided will be treated confidentially and no identifying information will be required.

One hundred and sixty (160) copies of questionnaire were distributed and administered to the participants. Those who could read and write in English were given the questionnaire to fill and return. Those who could not read and write in English were excluded from the study. Data collection lasted for a period of one month and all the questionnaires were filled properly as the researcher and research assistance went through the questionnaire after collecting from each participant, asked questions when an item of the questionnaire was not filled or filled incorrectly, the questionnaires were returned upon filling which was used for analysis.

Data Analysis

The study was a survey that adopted a correlation design. Based on the foregoing, the statistics used for the data analysis was Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient

Statistics. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient Statistics is used to test the linear relationship between the independent variables (spiritual involvement and social support) on the dependent variable (perceived stress). The data was analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences, SPSS version 26. Significance was accepted at $P < .05$.

Results

The results of the statistical analysis of the data obtained in the study are presented in the order in which the hypotheses were tested in the tables below.

Test of Hypotheses

Table 1: Summary of Correlation between Spiritual involvement and Perceived Stress among the Christian Clergy in Makurdi, Benue State

Source	Mean	Std.	r	Sig	N
Spirituality	6.9636	2.96188	-.317	.014	160
Perceived Stress	3.2417	1.44138	-1		

Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2 tailed).

The result presented in table 1 indicated a negative significant relationship between spirituality and perceived stress among the Christian clergy in Makurdi, Benue State at (Mean = 6.9, 3.2; SD = 2.9, 1.4; $r = -.317$, Sig = .014 $P < .05$). This result revealed that as spirituality is increasing, the Christian clergy perceived stress is reducing at (Mean = 6.9/3.2). Also, the result shows a negative relationship between spirituality and perceived stress at ($r = -.317$; -1) among the Christian clergy in Makurdi, Benue State. This shows that an increase in spirituality would lead to a decrease in perceived stress among the Christian clergy in Makurdi, Benue State.

Table 2: Summary of Pearson Moment Correlation between Social Support and Perceived Stress among the Christian clergy in Makurdi, Benue State

Source	Mean	Std. D	r	Sig	N
Social support	5.6102	2.8188	-.319	.013	160
Perceived Stress	2.3721	1.28769	-1		

Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2 tailed).

The result presented in table 2 indicated a negative significant relationship between social support and perceived stress among the Christian clergy in Makurdi, Benue State at (Mean = 5.6, 2.3; Std. D = 2.8, 1.2; $r = -.319$, Sig = .013 $P < .05$). This result revealed that as social support is increasing, the Christian clergy in Makurdi, Benue State perceived stress is reducing at (Mean = 5.6/2.3). Also, the result shows a negative relationship between social support and perceived stress at ($r = -.319$; -1) among the Christian clergy in Makurdi, Benue State. This shows that an increase in social support would lead to a decrease in perceived stress among the Christian clergy in Makurdi, Benue State.

Table 3: Summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation showing the relationship between spiritual involvement and Social Support among the Christian clergy in Makurdi, Benue State

Source	Mean	Std. D	r	Sig	N
SI	6.9636	2.96188	.907	.000	160
SS	3.2417	1.44138	+1		

Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2 tailed).

From the result shown above in hypothesis three, which investigated whether spiritual involvement will significantly correlate with social support among the Christian clergy in Makurdi, Benue State was accepted. From the result of the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient Statistics the result indicated positive significant relationship spirituality involvement and social support among the Christian clergy in Makurdi, Benue State at (Mean = 6.9, 3.2; Std. D = 2.9, 1.4; $r = .907$, Sig = .000 $P < .05$). This result revealed that spirituality involvement and social support increased positively (Mean = 6.9/3.2). Also, the result shows a positive relationship between spiritual involvement and social support at ($r = .907$; 1) among the Christian clergy in Makurdi, Benue State.

Discussion

The first hypothesis of this study was tested to find out if spiritual involvement will significantly correlate with perceived stress among the Christian clergy in Makurdi, Benue State. Findings revealed a significant negative correlation between spiritual involvement and perceived stress among the Christian clergy in Makurdi, Benue State ($r = -.317$; $p < .05$). This is an indication that spiritual involvement resulted in experiencing reduced perceived stress among the Christian clergy in Makurdi, Benue State. This result also suggests that higher spiritual involvement was linked to reduction in perceived stress which in turn resulted in experiencing reduced perceived stress among the Christian clergy in Makurdi, Benue State and as the more spiritually involved the clergies are, the more reduction of perceived stress they feel. This finding corresponds with those of Ozgul et al. (2021) and Daisy (2018) whose finding indicated that higher levels of spiritual involvement are associated with lower levels of perceived stress. The greater spiritual involvement is linked to lower levels of perceived stress. The finding of this work is in support with the Dialectical Behaviour Theory which is rooted in the idea that clergies with difficulties managing stress can benefit from learning specific coping strategies including working with clergy who encounter high levels of stress and challenging situations on a regular basis. The reduction in stress using spiritual involvement may have been reduced through the component of mindfulness that emphasizes the practice of being fully present, aware, and non-judgmental in the present moment and also emotion regulation which is a key virtue a clergy should possess.

The second hypothesis of this study was tested to find out if social support will significantly correlate with perceived stress among the Christian clergy in Makurdi, Benue State. The result of the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient Statistics revealed a significant negative correlation between social support and perceived stress among the Christian clergy in Makurdi, Benue State ($r = -.319$; $p < .05$). The finding of the result also suggests that increase in perceived stress will equally result to decrease in social support. This result finding is in line with the findings of Lawrence et al., (2022), Desmond and Maria-Chidi (2020) and David et al., (2018) who reported a significant negative relationship between social support and perceived stress. According to transactional theory of perceived

stress, it explained perceived stress as “a phenomenon that involves both cognitive and behavioral responses that individuals use in an attempt to manage internal and/or external stressors perceived to exceed their personal resources. This helps to understand the result of the finding which explains that the support one can get from social networks can help the Christian clergy cope with stress. The researcher, in consonance with the research outcomes, concludes that spiritual involvement and social support are some of the coping strategies to relieve stress among the Christian clergy. Therefore, clinicians should channel more of their therapeutic energy towards this stress coping mechanism among the Christian clergy.

The third hypothesis of this study was tested to find out if spiritual involvement will significantly correlate with social support among the Christian clergy was accepted. Findings revealed of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient Statistics revealed a significant correlation between spiritual involvement and social support among the Christian clergy in Makurdi, Benue State ($r=.907$; $p<.01$). This means that when spiritual involvement increases, social support also increases among the participants. The finding of this study is in support with the findings of Knappe et al. (2019) and Xiangpu et al. (2022) which revealed a significant relationship between spiritual involvement and social support. According to Dialectical Behaviour Theory which is rooted in the idea that clergies with difficulties managing stress can benefit from learning specific coping strategies including working with clergy who encounter high levels of stress and challenging situations on a regular basis. The reduction in stress using spiritual involvement may have been reduced through the component of mindfulness that emphasizes the practice of being fully present, aware, and non-judgmental in the present moment and also emotion regulation which is a key virtue a clergy should possess. For example, a clergy who practices spiritual involvement when faced with stress will have reduced stress. This explained to a large extent the reason for the negative significant correlation, which means that spiritual involvement aids in reducing stress among the Christian clergy in Makurdi, Benue State.

Conclusion

The result of this study suggests that spiritual involvement and social support are resources that help to strengthen the Christian clergy in the storms of stress. This study will prove useful in expanding our understanding of how Christian clergy handle stress through spiritual involvement and social support. However, this information can be used by clinical psychologists to develop targeted interventions aimed at ameliorating stress among the clergy.

Recommendations

- i. It is recommended that clinicians should conduct empirical research on a larger scale in this area and on the topic in regards to spiritual involvement and social support on perceived stress among the Christian clergy in Nigeria.
- ii. It is equally recommended that government should include counselling services in hospitals in Nigeria that will counsel and educate especially the clergies on the need of spiritual involvement and social support to perceived stress.
- iii. Based on the findings from this study, the researcher recommends that churches should collaborate with family therapist to offer sessions to all members of the clergy.

Contribution to Knowledge

This study has contributed to knowledge in the following ways:

- i. The research study provides a valuable collection of ideas and facts that can be of importance to clinical psychologist, schools, organizations, researchers, entrepreneurs,

lecturers and students in comprehending spirituality and social support on perceived stress among the Christian clergy.

- ii. Also, this study contributes to knowledge by establishing the positive significant correlation of spiritual involvement and social support on perceived stress among the Christian clergy. Most of these studies conducted in various nations around the globe all posited that spiritual involvement and social support have a positive correlation on perceived stress among the Christian clergy.
- iii. This study therefore provides a basis for research works and findings in these nations to be applied in clinical practice, institutions and organizations alike in Nigeria.

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